

forestry plants. *Philaenus spumarius* is the principal insect vector of this pathogen bacterium in Italy. We developed a Maxent model to detect the potential distribution of *X. fastidiosa* and *P. spumarius* in the Mediterranean basin. Maxent models achieved excellent levels of predictive performance as can be seen from AUC, TSS and AUC_{diff} values for both the organisms. Species distribution models showed a high probability of *X. fastidiosa* in Portugal, Spain, Italy, Southern France, Corsica, Albania, Montenegro, Greece and Turkey as well as all countries of Northern Africa and the Middle East. Maxent models also showed that *P. spumarius* was widespread in all countries of Europe, Northern Africa and the Middle East. *P. spumarius* could spread *X. fastidiosa* in all countries of the Mediterranean basin but, cold winter temperature seems to limit the spread of this pathogen bacterium in all countries located beyond the south of France. Our study highlights that *X. fastidiosa* may overcome the current boundaries outside Italy. Given the potentially high risk, the Phytosanitary Services of the listed nations are considering stringent phytosanitary measures to avoid the introduction of the bacterium in their own countries.

MONITORING OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA IN AN ITALIAN PEST-FREE AREA (LATIUM REGION). V. Modesti, N. Pucci, S. Lucchesi, L. Campus, S. Loreti. *Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Centro di ricerca per la patologia vegetale (CREA-PAV), via C. G. Bertero, 22 - 00156 Roma, Italy. E-mail: nicoletta.pucci@crea.gov.it*

The occurrence of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* on olive trees in the Salento area (Southern Italy) represent one of the most serious plant health emergencies of recent years in which the entire European Union have had to deal with. A monitoring plan for preventive purposes in the entire national territory was planned by the Italian Ministry of Agriculture by transposing the EU guidelines that foresee the measures to prevent introduction and spread of *X. fastidiosa*. As an example of 'pest-free' area is reported the experience of Latium region, in order to control the sanitary status of the territory and investigate on the presence/absence of *X. fastidiosa*. Taking into account that analyses were mainly focused on asymptomatic plant material, the diagnosis was based on the use of molecular methods characterized by high specificity and sensitivity: real-time PCR. Two assays based on the primers selected on the *rimM* gene and on the primers from the gene encoding the HL protein were used. These methods allowed to exclude the presence of *X. fastidiosa* in the processed samples in spite of the observation of some host plants with suspicious symptoms. An in wide comparison of the adopted approaches, by checking their analytical sensitivity and specificity, showed that the real-time PCR based on *rimM* selected primers was the most accurate for monitoring activity as it does not cause undetermined results when compared to the other real-time PCR (gene encoding HL protein). Other techniques, such as LAMP-PCR, are taken into account to improve the procedures by maintaining the performance of high sensitivity/specificity and in view of direct application in the field.

DETECTION OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA: VALIDATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF ROUTINE TESTING METHODS. G. Loconsole¹, D. Boscia², O. Potere¹, S. Zicca², G. Altamura², F. Palmisano³, V.N. Savino¹, M. Saponari². ¹Dipartimento di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti, Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, I-70126 Bari, Italy. ²Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante, SS Bari - 70126 Bari, Italy. ³Centro di Ricerca, Sperimentazione e Formazione in Agricoltura, Via Cisternino 281 - 70100 Locorotondo (BA), Italy. E-mail: giuliana.loconsole@uniba.it

Accurate and early detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* (*Xf*) is a major challenge due to the wide range of host plants (different matrices/tissues, rate of host colonization) and the occurrence of symptomless bacterial infections. The recent establishment of this exotic plant pathogenic bacterium in the EU territory and the large panel of EU susceptible host plants increased the need for rapid diagnostic tools suitable for processing large number of samples and from different sources. Although, several approaches are currently available for the detection of *Xf* in the host plants and vectors, there is a need for harmonized protocols and user-friendly diagnostic tests. In this study, we compared the sensitivity and the reliability of a selected panel of currently available protocols (ELISA, PCR, qPCR), in comparison with novel approaches based on automatized diagnostic platform and on DTBIA and LAMP-based assays. The overall results showed that: (i) although resulting in different diagnostic sensitivity all the approaches tested were able to detect the bacterium in samples from symptomless plants; (ii) Real-time LAMP assay based using crude plant sap can represent a rapid and reliable screening test; (iii) Real-time quantitative PCR assays had the higher diagnostic and analytical sensitivity; (iv) the use of automatized platform allowed to prepare PCR-templates with high and standardized quality for highly reliable diagnostic results; (v) DTBIA had the lowest diagnostic sensitivity, yet representing a useful approach when movement of *Xf* infected materials is limited due to the phytosanitary regulations.

TEST PERFORMANCE STUDY FOR VALIDATION OF DETECTION METHODS OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA. S. Loreti¹, N. Pucci¹, M. Saponari², G. Loconsole³, F. Gaffuri⁴, V. Modesti¹, S. Lucchesi¹, O. Potere³. ¹Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Centro di ricerca per la patologia vegetale (CREA-PAV), via C. G. Bertero, 22 - 00156 Roma, Italy. ²Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante, Sede Secondaria di Bari - 70126 Bari, Italy. ³Dipartimento di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti, Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, 70126 Bari, Italy. ⁴Laboratorio Fitopatologico SFR c/o Fondazione Minoprio, Viale Raimondi, 56 - Vertemate con Minoprio 22070 (CO), Italy. E-mail: stefania.loreti@crea.gov.it

Xylella fastidiosa, a xylem-limited bacterium of the *Xanthomonadaceae* family, was recently associated with the "Olive Quick Decline Syndrome" (OQDS) widespread in the Salento area (Southern Italy). The rapid emergence of this regulated quarantine pathogen in new areas imposes the application of official diagnostic methods aimed to prevent its spread in other Italian regions and the movement of latently infected plant material. The present study summarizes the results of a test-performance study (TPS) to validate, at a national level, detection methods of *X. fastidiosa* by involving sixteen Italian laboratories that includes several Plant Protection Services (PPS), SELGE, UniMi, UniCT, CRSFA, CIHEAM. A working group was constituted, that organized: i) a PRE-TEST for the establishment of analytical-sensitivity of each method and repeatability, analytical-specificity, relative accuracy, ii) the final TPS to detect the reproducibility of the selected methods. The activity of the pre-test highlighted a higher analytical-sensitivity from samples of total-DNA with respect crude-extracts. In particular, LAMP-PCR was more sensitive than ELISA tests from crude-extracts. Using total-DNA, duplex (based on *rimM* and on *cox* primers) and single real-time PCR (*rimM* primers) resulted in the most sensitive methods followed by LAMP-PCR and, finally, conventional PCR (primers RST31/RST33). The high values of relative-accuracy and reproducibility (among 92-100% for both) confirmed a high reliability of duplex/single real-time PCRs and LAMP-PCR from total-DNA. LAMP-PCR from crude extracts gave values of accuracy and reproducibility respectively of 78% and 87% resulting a promising assay for its friendly and on-site-based use, thus implementing